

Information form for participants

This document gives you information about the study “**Current practices for the development and maintenance of the digital twin software artifacts**”. Before the study begins, it is important that you learn about the procedure followed in this study and that you provide your informed consent for voluntary participation. Please, read this document carefully.

Context

This study is part of the research activities of the Work Package 3 of the ‘Digital Twin’ research project¹, which is funded through NWO TTW² grant. The Work Package 3 of this project is a collaboration among Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e), Tilburg University (TiU), and industrial partners. The research team consists of Hossain Muhammad Muctadir (TU/e), David Manrique Negrin (TU/e), Raghavendran Gunasekaran (TiU), Prof.dr. Mark van den Brand (TU/e), Dr.ir. Loek Cleophas (TU/e), and Prof.dr.ir. Boudewijn Haverkort (TiU). In the following text, this group is referred to as DT WP3.

This research activity is led by Hossain Muhammad Muctadir, a PhD candidate under the supervision of Mark van den Brand and Loek Cleophas.

Aim and benefit of the study

This study intends to understand how various software artifacts used in digital twins are developed and maintained. This information will be used to identify common patterns and current trends in the development as well as maintenance lifecycle of digital twins. These patterns may include but are not limited to,

- Software architecture
- Communication among persons and/or organizations
- Development methodologies
- Tooling and platforms
- Communication protocols
- Commonly faced technical challenges

in so far as they concern digital twins.

The outcome of this study will be used to identify potential high-impact areas and focus future research activities there.

Interview Procedure

During this study, semi-structured interviews will be performed. This means that the topic of the interview and a set of related questions will be predetermined. However, the questions may not be strictly followed, rather they will act as a guidance for the conversation.

A short text explaining the topic of the interview will be made available to the interviewee as early as possible. This will not only create more transparency around the interview, but also allow the interviewee time for preparation. The topics of the interview may include the

¹ <https://www.digital-twin-research.nl/research/research-project-3/>

² <https://www.nwo.nl/toegepaste-en-technische-wetenschappen-ttw>

use-cases of the digital twin, involvement of the interviewee in the development of the corresponding digital twin, software development methodologies and challenges. During the interview, all participants are encouraged to use visual aids (i.e., pictures, diagrams) for explaining complex technical concepts.

The interview may be conducted online using Microsoft Teams or in person. During the interview, it will be recorded (audio and/or video) and interviewer may take notes.

Risks

The study, to the best of the interviewers' knowledge, does not involve any personal risks, detrimental side effects, or cause discomfort.

Duration

The total duration of the interview will be at most an hour. The first and last five minutes will be used respectively for introduction and conclusion. The rest of the time will be used for the interview guided by a predefined set of questions. Since this is a semi-structured interview and questions may arise based on the answer of the interviewee, it is not feasible to provide an accurate time distribution for the core part of the interview.

Participants

The participants include both the interviewer(s) and the interviewee. During the interview, there will be at most two interviewers present who are researchers from the DT WP3 project. If there are two interviewers, one of them will conduct the interview. The other one will take notes and may ask questions occasionally. However, the interviewee may choose to have only one interviewer to be present.

The interviewee is chosen for his/her role in research or development of a prominent digital twin, which is being used in research or solving industrial use-cases.

Voluntary

Participation is completely voluntary. The interviewee can refuse to participate without giving any reasons and stop the participation at any time during the interview. It is also possible to withdraw the permission to use the recorded information up to 24 hours after they were recorded. None of this will have any negative consequences whatsoever.

Data usage, confidentiality, and privacy

This study has been approved by the Ethical Review Board³ of Eindhoven University of Technology.

During this study, the explicitly collected personally identifiable data are name, email address, workplace information, and role at workplace. However, during the interview further personal information might come up. Since the interview will be recorded (i.e., audio, video), this personal information will be recorded. These recordings will be securely stored using TU/e infrastructure (i.e., TU/e GitLab, Microsoft Stream/OneDrive instance of TU/e) for up to one year. The access to this content will be strictly maintained. They will be

³ <https://www.tue.nl/en/our-university/about-the-university/integrity/tue-ethical-review-board/>

accessible only by researchers from DT WP3 project (Hossain Muctadir, David Manrique, Raghavendran Gunasekaran, Loek Cleophas, Boudewijn Haverkort and Mark van den Brand). The audio and video recordings will not be distributed further and will not be played back in the presence of persons other than the researchers.

The information collected during the interview (i.e., audio/video recording, notes) will be used in scientific analysis, and the results will be made available as a scientific publication. All personally identifiable information will be discarded before analyzing the data. Moreover, the researchers will do their best to ensure the secrecy of personal data of the interviewee so that they do not end up in any publication.

Further information

Hossain Muctadir (email: h.m.muctadir@tue.nl) is the contact person for further inquiries regarding this study, the study design, and the results.

In case of any complaints about this study, please contact the supervisors, Mark van den Brand (m.g.j.v.d.brand@tue.nl) or Loek Cleophas (l.g.w.a.cleophas@tue.nl). It is also possible to report irregularities related to scientific integrity to confidential advisors of the TU/e⁴.

⁴ <https://www.tue.nl/en/our-university/about-the-university/integrity/scientific-integrity/>

Informed consent form

Study “**Current practices for the development and maintenance of the digital twin software artifacts**”

- I have read and understood the information of this form.
- I have been given the opportunity to ask questions. My questions are sufficiently answered, and I had sufficient time to decide whether I participate.
- I know that my participation is completely voluntary. I know that I can refuse to participate and that I can stop my participation at any time during the study, without giving any reasons. I know that I can withdraw permission to use my data up to 24 hours after the data have been recorded.
- I agree to voluntarily participate in this study.
- I know that information that can be used to personally identify me or my responses in this study will not be shared with anyone outside of the DT WP3 team.

- I do
 do not

give permission to make my anonymized recorded data available in scientific publications.

Certificate of consent

I, (NAME)
want and provide consent to participate in this study.

Participant’s Signature

Date